

UDC: 616.248.036:576.858

*Shakhova O.O., Tarnavska S.I., Mogyla Yu.O., Binkovskiy A.A., German K.V., Melnychuk M.A.**Department of Pediatrics and Children's Infectious Diseases**Bukovinian State Medical University, Chernivtsi, Ukraine*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14634016>

INFLUENCE OF ACUTE RESPIRATORY VIRAL INFECTIONS ON THE COURSE OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA IN CHILDREN

Abstract.

The role of infection in the development of bronchial asthma (BA) and its exacerbations is currently not in doubt, as are the notions of its initiating and protective effects. Numerous studies give reasons to consider respiratory viral infection (RIV) as an important factor in the formation of this disease with the subsequent triggering role of exacerbation attacks. Respiratory viruses are one of the main factors that can cause airway obstruction, there is a direct connection between asthma exacerbations and acute viral diseases, including their seasonal increases. It has been proven that viral infection in children with atopic constitution is an inducer of development, as well as a frequent trigger factor for exacerbations.

Key words. *Bronchial asthma, children, acute respiratory viral infections.*

Viral respiratory infections are a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, making them a serious public health problem. During infection, respiratory viruses, including influenza viruses, SARS-CoV-2, and respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), trigger an antiviral immune response, particularly by enhancing inflammatory responses that play a critical role in their pathogenesis. Viral infections profoundly affect the immune system and can induce immune signatures that persist after the acute phase of infection and potentially have a significant impact on the clinical course [1].

Asthma is a major public health problem with an enormous social and economic burden affecting 300 million people worldwide. Viral respiratory infections are a major cause of acute asthma exacerbations and contribute to the development of asthma in young children at high risk and with a susceptible genetic background. A history of wheezing associated with respiratory viral infections in early life is one of the main risk factors for later development of asthma, along with sensitization to aeroallergens in early life and a family history of asthma and allergy, which reflects a genetic predisposition. Respiratory viral infections are also the main cause of asthma exacerbations in children and adults [2].

It is believed that VRIs contribute to the development of asthma. A number of studies indicate the involvement of inflammation caused by VRI in the pathogenesis of asthma. For example, infections such as respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), human parainfluenza virus (hPIV), coronaviruses (CoV), human rhinovirus (HRV), and others in children with asthma can lead to exacerbations requiring hospitalization. These viruses cause inflammation of the epithelium of the respiratory tract, which can contribute to sensitization to aeroallergens and the development of an asthmatic phenotype [3]. Respiratory viruses also activate pro-inflammatory mediators, such as TNF- α/β , IL-1, IL-6, IL-8, which enhance an immune response similar to the Th2-helper response in patients with asthma. They are able to reduce the production of interferons, allowing

themselves to remain in the body for a long time. In patients with co-morbidities such as asthma or COPD, this increases the risk of chronic inflammation, which can contribute to permanent tissue damage and disease progression [3].

Respiratory syncytial virus is one of the most common causes of bronchiolitis in infants under two years of age and contributes to the development of asthma and its exacerbations later in life. RSV is often associated with severe asthma, while RV is more likely to cause exacerbations in older children. The primary infection occurs through inhalation and spreads to the lower respiratory tract, which is accompanied by the release of a wide range of inflammatory mediators [4].

Inflammation is an integral part of the body's immune response to fight infection. Respiratory viruses are detected by pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) in epithelial and immune cells that find specific pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) on the virus. In general, many surface and intracellular PRRs are activated during viral infection and can trigger intracellular signaling cascades that increase the expression of several proinflammatory and antiviral genes [3]. Type I interferons (INFs) (primarily IFN- α and IFN- β) and type III interferons are innate antiviral cytokines secreted by infected cells to trigger the transcription of IFN-stimulated genes (ISGs) that can disrupt the viral cycle of infection. In addition to directly controlling viral replication, IFN- α and IFN- β stimulate inflammation by recruiting and activating leukocytes. IAV and RSV can interfere with IFN production and bypass IFN signaling by expressing nonstructural proteins that can antagonize IFN or ISG. Although an effective IFN response is critical to suppress viral replication early in infection, persistent or enhanced production of type I and type III IFNs can suppress epithelial cell recovery and impair macrophage-associated antibacterial responses after viral infection [3].

Acute allergic reactions cause the activation of eosinophils and T helper type 2 (Th2) cells, which stimulate B cells to produce IgE with the help of IL-4. These processes are accompanied by the release of

mediators, such as histamine, leukotrienes, and kinins, which cause contraction of smooth muscles, increased permeability of blood vessels, and mucus production by glands. In addition, Toll-like receptor 4 on epithelial cells responds to infectious and allergic triggers by activating inflammation. People with asthma have lower levels of immune response proteins called interferons than others, which increases their risk of getting sick from viruses. The ability to prevent the virus from multiplying in the lungs is reduced, which can lead to damage to lung cells. Low levels of antiviral factors in children with asthma increase vulnerability to viral diseases at an early stage, especially in those prone to atopy [5].

Chronic inflammation of the airways causes structural changes known as remodeling. This includes goblet cell hyperplasia, basement membrane thickening, and subepithelial fibrosis. IL-4 and IL-5 cause eosinophilia, which contributes to exacerbation of asthma. Epidemiological data show that lung infections at the initial stage of life, spanning from a couple to several years, significantly increase the likelihood of developing asthma in the future [5].

Up to 70% of children with asthma experience exacerbations after viral infections. Severe asthma attacks are associated with slowed breathing development, increased disease consequences, and significant financial costs. The main dangers are previous exacerbations, allergies, viral diseases and poor asthma treatment. Data show that viral respiratory infections not only aggravate asthma, but also contribute to its development at an early age. Although the causal relationship between viruses and asthma remains unresolved, it is clear that their interaction with allergic sensitization is a key mechanism. The development of new therapeutic approaches aimed at modifying the immune response and reducing exposure to viruses is essential to reducing the burden of asthma. Understanding the molecular mechanisms of viral induction of asthma exacerbations may allow identifying risk groups, delaying first infections, and developing effective strategies for prevention and treatment [2, 4].

Conclusions. In summary, a balanced self-limited inflammatory response is critical for controlling pathogen replication and promoting the development of

adaptive immune responses. However, in severe respiratory viral infections, this balance is disrupted, leading to excessive activation of various inflammatory pathways that contribute to tissue damage, pulmonary dysfunction, and even death. Despite the magnitude of the problem caused by respiratory viruses in acute asthma, there are no specific vaccines or treatments. Important questions will need to be addressed, including optimal drug delivery, including whether it should be intranasally or directly into the airways. Inflammation in viral respiratory infections is a vital part of immune defense, but its unregulated activation can cause serious pathology, including lung damage, development of chronic diseases and even fatal complications. Understanding the molecular mechanisms of inflammation, the role of leukocytes and the influence of viral mediators on the immune response is key to the development of new therapeutic strategies.

Reference list

1. Kombe Kombe, AJ, Fotoohabadi, L., Gerasimova, Y., Nanduri, R., Lama Tamang, P., Kandala, M., & Kelesidis, T. (2024). The Role of Inflammation in the Pathogenesis of Viral Respiratory Infections. *Microorganisms*, 12(12), 2526. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms12122526>.
2. Ahanchian, H., Jones, CM, Chen, YS, & Sly, PD (2012). Respiratory viral infections in children with asthma: do they matter and can we prevent them?. *BMC pediatrics*, 12, 147. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2431-12-147>.
3. Tavares, LP, Nijmeh, J., & Levy, BD (2023). Respiratory viral infection and resolution of inflammation: Roles for specialized pro-resolving mediators. *Experimental biology and medicine* (Maywood, NJ), 248(19), 1635–1644. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15353702231199082>.
4. Hansbro, NG, Horvat, JC, Wark, PA, & Hansbro, PM (2008). Understanding the mechanisms of viral-induced asthma: new therapeutic directions. *Pharmacology & therapeutics*, 117(3), 313–353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pharmthera.2007.11.002>.
5. Arora, P., & Ansari, SH (2019). Role of Various Mediators in Inflammation of Asthmatic Airways. *IntechOpen*. doi: 10.5772/intechopen.84357.